

Experimental Demonstration of OpenFlow-based Dynamic Restoration in Elastic Optical Networks on GENI Testbed

Lei Liu⁽¹⁾, Wei-Ren Peng⁽²⁾, Ramon Casellas⁽³⁾, Takehiro Tsuritani⁽⁴⁾, Itsuro Morita⁽⁴⁾,
Ricardo Martínez⁽³⁾, Raúl Muñoz⁽³⁾, S. J. Ben Yoo⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾Univ. of California, Davis, One Shields Ave, CA 95616, USA, liulei@ieee.org, sbyoo@ucdavis.edu

⁽²⁾Futurewei Technologies, 2330 Central Expressway, Santa Clara, CA 95050, USA

⁽³⁾Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Castelldefels, Barcelona, Spain

⁽⁴⁾KDDI R&D Laboratories Inc., 2-1-15 Ohara, Fujimino-shi, Saitama 356-8502, Japan

Abstract We present OpenFlow-enabled dynamic restoration in elastic optical networks, detailing the restoration framework and algorithm, failure isolation mechanism, OpenFlow protocol extensions, and quantitatively presenting the restoration performance via the experimental validation on the Global Environment for Network Innovations (GENI) testbed.

Introduction

The role of the control plane is critically important in dynamic elastic optical networks (EONs) for restoring services in case of link failures. Recently, Software-Defined Networking (SDN), in particular, the OpenFlow architecture and its associated protocol have attracted strong interest from both academia and industry.

Although a number of previous works have investigated OpenFlow-based EONs, these works mainly focused on dynamic connection provisioning¹⁻³. To the best of our knowledge, only the works in^{4, 5} investigated OpenFlow-enabled restoration in EONs. Ref.⁴ presented a proof-of-concept demonstration of OpenFlow-controlled dynamic recovery for only one failed connection on a real EON testbed employing flexible transmitter (Tx) and receiver (Rx). Ref.⁵ proposed a fast OpenFlow-based restoration scheme to minimize the parallel hardware configuration delay. However, the physical impairments are not considered in⁵. Since the restoration path usually has a different fiber length and hop count compared with the working path, the consideration of physical layer impairments, modulation formats or even bandwidth squeezed restoration⁶ is important to attain successful service recovery.

In this work, we investigate OpenFlow-based dynamic restoration in EONs by considering all the above factors into account. We propose an OpenFlow-based failure isolation mechanism and a new OpenFlow OFPT_ALARM message. Based on these, a two-phase restoration routing, spectrum, and modulation format assignment (RSMA) algorithm is presented. More importantly, an experiment is carried out on the Global Environment for Network Innovations (GENI)⁷ testbed, which includes many GENI racks, regional and national backbone networks around the United States. This allows validating the overall feasibility and

provides valuable insights into its potentials for possible deployment in the future.

Fig. 1:(a) DDO-OFDM Tx; (b) DDO-OFDM Rx; (c) Packet format for OFPT_ALARM

OpenFlow-based EON with flexible Tx/Rx

The data plane of an OpenFlow-based EON includes bandwidth-variable wavelength cross-connects (BV-WXCs) and flexible Tx/Rx. As in our previous work³, the Tx utilized the direct-detected optical orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (DDO-OFDM)⁸ technique. However, the proposed restoration scheme applies to any other transmission techniques such as coherent OFDM, coherent optical WDM or Nyquist WDM. Fig.1(a) describes the Tx and Rx algorithms for DDO-OFDM supported by advanced digital signal processing and discussed in detail in our previous work³. The network elements (NEs) are configured by OpenFlow agents, and a centralized OpenFlow controller (e.g. NOX) is used to communicate with all OpenFlow agents through the extended OpenFlow protocol, as described in detail below.

OpenFlow protocol extensions, failure isolation, and restoration procedure

The break-before-make scheme is adopted, wherein the working path is deleted prior to set up the restoration path. Here, we assume that each BV-WXC is equipped with optical power monitors to detect the loss of light when a link failure happens. The link failure notification to NOX is achieved by either extending the

OFPT_PORT_STATUS message or introducing a new OFPT_ALARM message. In this work, we used the latter approach, where the packet format of such a new message is shown in Fig.1(c). By using the concept of "unnumbered link" from GMPLS, the OFPT_ALARM message carries the Datapath ID field (8 bytes) for indicating the node address, and an interface ID field (4 bytes) for indicating the port associated to the failed link. Note that for a given connection, an upstream link failure may cause all downstream BV-WXCs to send out alarms. Therefore, a failure isolation mechanism is required in the NOX to determine the exact failed point. Thanks to its global view, the NOX can combine these affected links into a segment to check if it belongs to existing connections. If yes, the NOX localizes the first link of the segment as the failed point. After that, by excluding the failed link, the NOX performs a two-phase restoration RSMA algorithm (as detailed next), and then controls corresponding nodes to create a restoration path through extended *Flow Mod* messages, as previously investigated¹⁻³.

Two-phase restoration RSMA algorithm

Considering the fact that fully dynamic RSMA computation is complex and is likely to be CPU-intensive, as well as a single link failure may affect multiple connections, to reduce restoration time and to mitigate the effect of centralized restoration, we implement a two-phase restoration RSMA algorithm in the NOX, and we use the Q^2 factor⁸ as the signal quality indicator. In the first phase, the K -shortest paths for each source-destination pair are calculated. After that, pre-computed tables comprise the Q^2 factor values (in dB) and optical spectrum width (in GHz) information for given net data rates, modulation formats, path distances and hop counts are generated, which are the results of the simulation of DDO-OFDM transmission. For longer paths not considered during the off-line planning, the most robust modulation format is assigned to guarantee the signal quality at the Rx. In the second phase for dynamic restoration

path selection and resource assignment when a failure alarm is received, the NOX performs a lookup for pre-computed static planning tables and checks the pre-computed paths which do not include the failed link as the potential restoration paths. In this step, the NOX firstly tries to find restoration paths that can support the same data rate of the working path. If such a restoration path does not exist, the NOX then reduces the data rate and checks static planning tables again (i.e. bandwidth squeezed restoration). The NOX serves failed connections one by one, and if multiple combinations are possible with the same data rate, the criterion is to minimize the resulting optical spectrum.

Experimental setup, results and discussion

We set up an OpenFlow control plane network over the GENI testbed by using some GENI racks⁷, as shown in Fig.3(a), which is the snapshot of the FLACK GUI⁷. The emulated data plane comprises 14 nodes, which are connected through emulated fiber links with different lengths, as the topology shown in Fig.3(a). All the nodes are connected to a dedicated NOX controller based on Ubuntu 10.04. The DWDM links are characterized by 128 individual slots of 6.25 GHz each. Linear standard single mode fiber (SSMF) links are assumed, featuring an attenuation of 0.2 dB/km and a chromatic dispersion coefficient of 16 ps/nm·km. The input power to fibers is 0dBm. We use $K=3$ for the K -shortest paths algorithm, restricted to a maximum number of 5 hops. For each link, the maximum span length is limited to 80 km. Each span contains an erbium doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) compensating exactly the loss of each span with a fixed noise figure of 6 dB. Each ROADM is modeled as a 4th-order Gaussian-shaped filter with its 3dB-bandwidth covering ~1.5 times the signal bandwidth. The target Q^2 factor is 8.53 dB⁸ which is the threshold of the hard-decision forward error correction. Different modulation formats such as 4-, 16- and 64-QAM, and various data rates including 10, 40, and 100 Gb/s are discussed. Figs.2(a)(b)(c) show the off-line network

Fig. 2: Q^2 factor (in dB) at the Rx for different distances and hop count corresponding to different modulation formats (4QAM, 16QAM, 64QAM) at (a) 10Gb/s, (b) 40Gb/s, (c) 100Gb/s DDO-OFDM transmissions

planning results for the restoration paths. Q^2 factors at the Rx side are measured for different distances and hop counts corresponding to different modulation formats (4-, 16-, 64QAM) at 10, 40, and 100Gb/s DDO-OFDM transmissions. Fig.3(b) shows the signal bandwidth for DDO-OFDM with different modulation formats. As expected, the 4QAM constellation is more robust to physical impairments, whereas the 64QAM constellation gives the best performance in terms of spectral efficiency. It can be observed that all the 4QAM cases are above the target Q^2 factor threshold, whereas when using 16QAM at 100 Gb/s, 64QAM at 40 Gb/s, and 64QAM at 100 Gb/s, the attainable distance is limited. These results are stored in the pre-computed static planning table in the NOX for dynamic restoration path selection.

In the experiment, we randomly set up connections in the network, and then emulate the link failure event to measure the control plane latency during restoration and the restorability. Failure alarms are generated which include identifiers of a randomly selected failed link, and are directly sent to the NOX to emulate link failure events. Fig.3(c) shows the Wireshark capture of an OFPT_ALARM message, which encapsulates the alarm type and the identifier of the failed link. When such a failure alarm is received, the NOX performs the two-phase RSMA computation as detailed above. If a restoration path is found, the NOX controls the nodes to set up the restoration path through extended *Flow Mod* messages. Fig.3(d) and Fig.3(e) show measured control plane restoration latencies and restorability (out of 1000 restoration connections), respectively. Note that the restoration latencies did not take

into account hardware configuration delay. These performance results validate the overall feasibility of the OpenFlow-controlled restoration in an EON with DDO-OFDM transmission.

Conclusions

In this paper, we presented OpenFlow-based dynamic connection restoration for a software-defined EON using DDO-OFDM transmission. The overall feasibility and efficiency of the proposed solutions, including the control framework, the failure isolation mechanism, the restoration algorithm, and protocol extensions are experimentally validated and quantitatively evaluated in terms of restoration latencies and restorability on the GENI testbed.

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Fig. 3:(a) GENI FLACK GUI; (b) Signal bandwidth and required spectrum slots for DDO-OFDM with different modulation formats³; (c) Wireshark capture of the new OFPT_ALARM message; (d) Control plane restoration latency; (e) Restorability under different network status (different resource utilization ratio).